

WAYS TO DEVELOP MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN TOURIST ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the tasks of marketing development in tourist organizations, the creation of a marketing program, the formation of tourism infrastructure and the development of market relations, the main work of tourist and hotel entities are considered.*

Keywords: *tourism organization, marketing program, market, resource, development, region, subject.*

ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены задачи развития маркетинга в туристских организациях, создание маркетинговой программы, формирование инфраструктуры туризма и развитие рыночных отношений, основная работа туристско-гостиничных субъектов.*

Ключевые слова: *организация туризма, маркетинговая программа, рынок, ресурс, развитие, регион, субъект.*

INTRODUCTION

To the objectives in the field of tourism in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-4861 the creation of national tourism products and their promotion in world markets, the formation of a positive image of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism requires the rapid development of marketing activities in this field [1]. This issue is especially relevant in a region rich in tourism resources like Samarkand. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, noted, "Taking into account the potential of Samarkand, the possibilities of tourism development are limitless."

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Increasing attention to tourism marketing means, first of all, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, to meet the needs of guests and to satisfy their needs for recreation, as well as to implement the policy of developing the population's inclination to travel. In this case, it is required to literally develop the principles of marketing in business entities that provide services to tourists. One of the important conditions for the development of marketing in tourism companies is to understand the specifics of tourism marketing. Marketing activity is characterized by its focus on the future, that is, modern all the actions of the enterprise in the market are organized not only on the basis of knowledge of today's consumer demand, but also on the basis of its changes and prospects. Adaptation of the general theory of marketing to the field of tourism and the development of appropriate research that takes into account its characteristics is the focus of many scientists. According to their emphasis, the distinctive feature of marketing in the field of tourism is defined as follows:

- The dependence of marketing on the external environment. Often, the formation of demand is

not related to the content of the tourist resource, but to its interpretation in the marketing infrastructure;

- The uniqueness of the tourist product and the services included in it. The consumption of tourist products is closely related to the volume, quality and content of services provided to tourists. In some cases, services may occupy the main part of the tourist product;
- A systematic approach to creating a tourist product. The tourist product is evaluated not only according to the service process of the tourist firm, but also according to the conditions created for tourists in the country;
- The level of development of mechanisms of production and consumption of tourist products. The effectiveness of the tourism sector is often determined by the attitude of all economic sectors of the country to tourism. For example, the development of agrotourism destinations depends primarily on positive views of tourism processes in agriculture;
- A clear distinction of the tourist season in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The climate of our country remains the main factor of familiarization with the available tourist resources and the convenience of their use at a certain time. In this regard, tourist companies are also adapted to seasonal activities;
- Lack of full use of opportunities and capacities of tourist organizations. The main goal of the tourism industry is to create the necessary conditions for any guest at any time. In this regard, it is envisaged that the capacity of the tourist-hotel complex will be adjusted to the maximum volume of the tourist flow, even to meet the highest demand for the types of hotels. This will certainly be associated with additional costs.

If we analyze the tourism policy in the city of Samarkand, we must admit that until recently the main focus was on foreign tourists. Developed tourist products, food and living conditions are all designed for foreign visitors. Today, the newly opened opportunities of domestic tourism have led to a turning point in the marketing activities of service providers. The development of historical and religious monuments, attractions, and recreation centers of Samarkand in accordance with the requirements of our citizens is being carried out rapidly.

The development of marketing activities in tourism should first of all start with service entities. Most of the city's tourism firms and hotels are small business entities. On the one hand, small business has many advantages and conveniences in terms of organization and finances, but on the other hand, the lack of labor resources and necessary knowledge and skills can cause problems in covering some tasks. In this regard, the leaders of tourist organizations have a number of tasks to organize and develop marketing activities. Let's touch on some of them.

The first and main task of marketing development is to distinguish marketing activities from ordinary business activities and to include them in the range of strategically important actions, that is, to focus on the marketing program. Actions of state management bodies aimed at the development of tourism only form the infrastructure of tourism, but the main work such as the development of market relations should be performed by tourist and hotel entities. In performing this task, the presence of an appropriate methodological approach to the creation of a marketing program is of great importance.

The second task is to carry out an active policy of monitoring the state of the tourism market. The head of the tourist company should try to determine the state of the market, indicators and their dynamics. It has become urgent to ensure that the marketing information

system is perfect in tourism companies. Why should foreign companies know more about the tourist market of Samarkand? Managers of tourist organizations are required to maintain an active marketing information policy. Active policy means independent search for information, analysis and, if necessary, becoming a disseminator of information.

The third task is to clarify the forms of organization of marketing service in tourist companies and to define the principles of its operation. It can be noted that one of the reasons for the low effectiveness of marketing services in tourism companies and hotels today. With the creation of a marketing department, it cannot be said that the concept of marketing has been adopted. The form of marketing services in tourism should arise from the uniqueness and distinguishing features of the market and respond to them.

RESULTS

In fulfilling the above tasks, it is very important to carefully develop the scientific-methodical approach and use of modern scientific results. It is known to everyone that most tourist companies started their work on the basis of air ticket offices, that is, the uniqueness of tourist activity was not taken as the main principle when starting work. As a result, the integration of marketing functions during operations has become a more complex issue. Currently, the essence of the problem is that, although the application of modern marketing theory in tourism is relevant, the experience and opportunities of business entities in this field to put it into practice are limited. The number of employees in tourist companies and hotels in Samarkand is very small, and it is difficult to cover all marketing tasks. In this regard, in our opinion, The time has come for Uzbek scientists to create concise and simple guides for organizing marketing activities for tourist companies and hotels. We know that such experience has once been very effective in creating business plan methodology manuals for entrepreneurs. The manuals and recommendations that will be created will be useful for practitioners as they offer concrete solutions for marketing principles and organizational mechanisms in tourism organizations. Publishing and promoting a series of methodological materials in the field of tourism marketing can also be of great value in increasing marketing literacy. We know that such experience has once been very effective in creating business plan methodology manuals for entrepreneurs. The manuals and recommendations that will be created will be useful for practitioners as they offer concrete solutions for marketing principles and organizational mechanisms in tourism organizations. Publishing and promoting a series of methodological materials in the field of tourism marketing can also be of great value in increasing marketing literacy. We know that such experience has once been very effective in creating business plan methodology manuals for entrepreneurs. The manuals and recommendations that will be created will be useful for practitioners as they offer concrete solutions for marketing principles and organizational mechanisms in tourism organizations. Publishing and promoting a series of methodological materials in the field of tourism marketing can also be of great value in increasing marketing literacy.

DISCUSSION

We believe that it is appropriate to include specific offers in the forms of marketing services in tourist enterprises. Based on the peculiarities of tourism, it is necessary to combine the marketing tasks into two groups: the tasks of managing the regional tourism potential and the tasks of increasing the competitiveness of the company. Covering the tasks of the first group within the firm itself is both impossible and ineffective. No tourist company or hotel can perform

these tasks independently. For this purpose, it is possible to use the services of special marketing and consulting centers that are active on a commercial basis. The tasks of the second group are based on local conditions, and it is possible to create a structure based on the capabilities of each enterprise. The importance of these tasks is that they can be standardized and reduced to specific job instructions. We also believe that it is necessary to offer various options of ready-made marketing services for entrepreneurs. Of course, the more options are offered, the easier it is for companies to organize a marketing service based on experience.

CONCLUSIONS

Our proposals are aimed at all scientists and are based on the integration of scientific developments carried out to date. At the same time, the introduction of the suggestions of practical leaders would also be an impetus in the application of marketing in the field. Open discussion of problems in tourist companies and hotels, exchange of ideas on their elimination and prevention, regular publication of recommendations of experts serve to increase the effectiveness of such activities.

The main thing is to create a platform for exchange of experience in marketing activities in tourism companies.

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